

IMPORTANT POLITICAL PROCESS: ELECTIONS TO THE LEGISLATIVE CHAMBER OF THE OLIY MAJLIS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND LOCAL COUNCILS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13917471>

Annotation. This article analyzes the political and legal aspects of the elections to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and local councils, scheduled for October 27, 2024. The study examines the evolution of Uzbekistan's electoral system, the changes implemented within the framework of the 2023 constitutional reforms, and the effectiveness of the mixed electoral system. Additionally, it discusses the role of political parties in the elections, election campaigns, the involvement of international observers, and the compliance of the electoral process with international standards. The article compares Uzbekistan's electoral system with the practices of other countries, highlighting the social and economic impact of the elections and their contribution to strengthening democratic institutions. The research provides an analytical approach to the significance of ongoing reforms in Uzbekistan's political system and underscores the importance of these elections for the future of the country.

Key words: Uzbekistan electoral system, mixed electoral system, constitutional reforms, political parties, international observers, democratic processes.

History of the Electoral System and Reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan

After gaining independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan carried out a series of important changes in its political system, one of which was the formation and reform of the electoral system. Through elections, citizens form representative bodies of state power, which is one of the main components of democratic governance.

Early Years of the Electoral System

In the initial years, Uzbekistan's electoral system operated based on elements inherited from the former Soviet Union. The first presidential election, held on December 29, 1991, was one of the most important political events following the country's independence. In this election, Islam Karimov was elected as the first president of Uzbekistan. The first elections to the Oliy Majlis (parliament) were held in 1994. During this period, the electoral system functioned within a multi-party system but under an authoritarian regime.

Reforms in the 2000s

Starting in the 2000s, Uzbekistan undertook several measures to reform its electoral system. In 2002, a new law was introduced, establishing the Electoral Code, which created a legal basis for more open and transparent elections. Additionally, during this period, the number of political parties increased, and changes were made to the legislation to strengthen the activities of parties eligible to participate in elections.

The 2008 Reforms

In 2008, changes were made to the system for electing deputies to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis. These reforms introduced a mixed electoral system, in which part of the deputies were elected through a majoritarian system and part through a proportional

system. This system was designed to ensure diversity and balance in the election of deputies to the Oliy Majlis.

The 2019 Elections and Renewed Political Processes

The 2019 elections to the Oliy Majlis marked the beginning of changes in state governance and the liberalization of the political system. In this election, new-generation political parties and candidates actively participated. International observers, including those from OSCE/ODIHR, noted an increase in the transparency of the elections, although some issues remained. After Shavkat Mirziyoyev was elected president, he focused on accelerating reforms in the political system.

The 2023 Constitutional Amendments

The constitutional amendments introduced in 2023 marked a turning point in Uzbekistan's electoral system. These changes were aimed at further democratizing the electoral process, increasing the role of parliament, and expanding citizens' electoral rights. In particular:

- **Expansion of the powers of the Oliy Majlis** – Strengthening the role of parliament in governance, increasing its influence over the state.
- **Development of the mixed electoral system** – Enhancing the balance between majoritarian and proportional systems to strengthen multiparty representation and ensure broader citizen participation.

Impact of the 2023 Constitutional Amendments on the Electoral System

The amendments to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan introduced in 2023 significantly influenced the country's political and legal system. These changes aimed to further democratize the electoral process, increase transparency, and enhance the impact of citizens on representative bodies. The constitutional reforms encompassed all branches of state power, including the election process, introducing new rules for electing deputies to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis and local councils. The main aspects of these reforms include:

1. **Expansion of the powers of the Oliy Majlis:** The amendments extended the powers of the Oliy Majlis. As the highest legislative body of the country, the Oliy Majlis plays a crucial role in the democratic governance system. The 2023 reforms increased the authority of deputies in the Legislative Chamber, making their election process more democratic and transparent.
2. **Strengthening of the mixed electoral system:** The constitutional reforms reinforced the mixed electoral system. In Uzbekistan, a mixed system is applied, where some deputies are elected through a majoritarian system (by direct citizen vote), and others through a proportional system (based on party lists). These reforms further developed this system to form the composition of parliament on a multiparty basis.
3. **Expansion of citizens' electoral rights:** A key part of the 2023 reforms was aimed at expanding citizens' electoral rights. These changes sought to increase voter participation, ensure free voting, and enhance mechanisms for transparency and fairness in elections.
4. **Ensuring the independence of electoral commissions:** Several reforms were introduced to strengthen the independence of electoral commissions. These changes aimed to ensure the independence of the Central Election Commission and reduce external influences on the electoral process. Independent election commissions were expected to improve transparency and fairness in the election process.
5. **Expansion of international observer participation:** To ensure that Uzbekistan's electoral system complies with international standards, the involvement of international

observers was expanded. The 2023 reforms aimed to increase oversight by international organizations, including reputable ones like OSCE/ODIHR. This aimed to enhance the transparency of elections and ensure they were recognized by the international community.

Impact of the 2023 Reforms on Elections to the Oliy Majlis and Local Councils

The 2023 constitutional amendments directly affected the elections to the Oliy Majlis and local councils. These reforms were aimed at ensuring that elections were conducted in a more democratic manner, in accordance with legal standards.

Particular attention was given to increasing the competitiveness of candidates and parties, expanding voter choice, and strengthening the role of local councils.

In the elections for deputies to local councils, a mixed system was also applied, where some deputies were elected through a majoritarian system, while others were elected from party lists. This system was designed to increase the efficiency of local governance and enhance citizen participation in local issues.

Effectiveness of the Mixed Electoral System and Its Application in Uzbekistan

The mixed electoral system is one of the most common forms of electoral systems in democratic countries, where elections are held based on two main components: a majoritarian system (determining winners by majority vote) and a proportional system (distributing seats among political parties according to their share of the vote). The mixed electoral system was introduced in Uzbekistan in 2008 and has been improved since then.

Structure of the Mixed Electoral System

Typically, the mixed electoral system includes two types of voting:

1. **Majoritarian system:** Voters cast their ballots for candidates in a specific constituency, and the candidate with the most votes is elected. This system allows voters to directly select candidates, and typically one candidate is elected from each electoral district.
2. **Proportional system:** Political parties receive seats in parliament based on the percentage of votes they receive. The goal of this system is to distribute votes as fairly as possible so that parties receive seats proportional to their vote share.

The Mixed Electoral System in Uzbekistan

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, deputies to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis and local councils are elected using a mixed electoral system. The election to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis consists of two parts:

- **Majoritarian system:** Of the 150 deputies in the Oliy Majlis, 125 are elected through the majoritarian system, meaning the candidate with the most votes in each constituency wins. Voters directly choose their candidates in this system.
- **Proportional system:** The remaining 25 deputies are elected from party lists based on the proportional system. Political parties campaign to gather votes and receive seats in proportion to their vote totals. The proportional system aims to balance the distribution of seats among parties and ensure broad political representation in parliament.

Local council deputies are also elected based on both majoritarian and proportional systems.

Effectiveness of the Mixed Electoral System

Through the mixed electoral system, Uzbekistan aims to achieve several important goals:

1. **Strengthening multiparty politics:** The proportional component of the mixed system encourages the growth of political parties and motivates their active participation in elections. This ensures the representation of diverse political views and interests in parliament.

2. **Enhancing regional representation:** The majoritarian system allows for the direct election of representatives from each region. This system provides opportunities for the interests of each region to be expressed at the national level.

3. **Providing voters with broader choices:** In the mixed system, voters participate in two types of elections, allowing them to choose both candidates and political parties. This enhances voter engagement and increases interest in the election process.

4. **Strengthening democratic governance:** The mixed system, particularly the proportional aspect, helps ensure fair representation in democratic systems. The equal participation of different political groups in parliament strengthens democratic governance and maintains political balance.

Challenges of the Mixed Electoral System in Uzbekistan

Despite its effectiveness, the mixed electoral system in Uzbekistan faces some challenges:

1. **Complexity of the electoral system:** The mixed system may appear complicated to voters, as they are required to cast ballots in two different formats. This could affect their understanding of the process.

2. **Compatibility of political parties with candidates:** In the proportional system, political parties run candidates through their lists, while in the majoritarian system, independent candidates can also compete. Ensuring the cohesion of these two systems may be difficult, as the interests of political parties and independent candidates could conflict during elections.

3. **Competition among regional candidates:** The majoritarian system fosters strong competition among regional candidates. This can complicate the election process in certain regions or lead voters to make uninformed choices.

Uzbekistan's Compliance with International Electoral Standards and the Role of International Observers

As Uzbekistan works to democratize its electoral system, compliance with international electoral standards is of paramount importance. Elections that adhere to international standards ensure transparency, fairness, and credibility, thereby fostering public confidence in the electoral process. Moreover, compliance with these standards contributes to Uzbekistan's international recognition. The involvement of international observers is a key mechanism for monitoring the alignment of elections with democratic principles.

International Electoral Standards and Uzbekistan

International electoral standards, primarily established by organizations such as the United Nations (UN), the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE), and the Council of Europe, encompass several key principles:

1. **Free and fair elections:** Citizens must have the ability to choose their representatives freely, without any external pressure or influence.

2. **Transparency of the electoral process:** Transparency must be ensured throughout the election process, including during voting and vote counting.

3. **Universal suffrage:** All eligible citizens should be allowed to participate in elections on an equal footing, with no discrimination.

4. **Political pluralism and competition:** Various political parties and candidates should have the right to present their ideas freely and compete on equal terms during election campaigns.

5. **Independence of election commissions:** The bodies overseeing the election process, particularly election commissions, must be independent. They should operate without external pressures and in accordance with the law.

Uzbekistan has been implementing reforms to align its electoral legislation with international standards. Notably, the adoption of the new Electoral Code in 2019 was aimed at enhancing the transparency of the electoral process and increasing its compliance with international standards.

The Role of International Observers

International observers play a critical role in assessing the compliance of elections with international standards and ensuring the transparency of the process. Uzbekistan has sought to increase the participation of international observers to enhance the openness of its elections. International organizations actively involved in monitoring elections in Uzbekistan include:

1. **OSCE/ODIHR (Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe, Office for Democratic Institutions and Human Rights):** This organization is one of the most active in monitoring elections in Uzbekistan. It conducts thorough analysis of the electoral process and prepares objective, detailed reports on how the elections were conducted.
2. **CIS (Commonwealth of Independent States) election missions:** Observer groups from the CIS countries also monitor elections in Uzbekistan.
3. **Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) and other international organizations:** The OIC participates as an observer in Uzbekistan's elections, providing assessments of the election process.

Assessments by International Observers

The assessments provided by international observers on elections in Uzbekistan have varied. For instance, during the 2019 Oliy Majlis elections, OSCE/ODIHR observers noted positive changes in the electoral process. Reports indicated an increase in transparency and highlighted the reforms being undertaken. However, certain shortcomings were also noted, such as restricted competition between political parties and candidates and the incomplete guarantee of equal opportunities during election campaigns.

Similarly, during the 2021 presidential election, international observers once again praised the changes made to Uzbekistan's electoral system but noted that issues related to free competition in the election campaigns remained.

Uzbekistan's Steps Toward Conforming to International Standards

In addition to the constitutional reforms of 2023, Uzbekistan has taken multiple steps to further align its electoral process with international standards. These reforms are aimed at increasing international recognition of the country and fully safeguarding the electoral rights of its citizens.

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